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Observing the Movement of Prime Numbers in a Prime-based Number Triangle:

'Kermit Primes'

Abstract:

A Pascal's Triangle was mapped to prime numbers and the placement of prime numbers propagated in the triangle was observed as a fluctuating offset was applied to the top of the triangle.

Methodology:

A spreadsheet was populated following the propagation rule we are familiar with in Pascal's Triangle, namely that each cell is the sum of the cell above and the cell to its right. (the two cells diagonally above when viewed from a 45° counterclockwise angle). Consecutive prime numbers were mapped into row 1 and column A, and cell B2 has been highlighted as the offset. This offset was manually manipulated to view how this affected where prime numbers were propagated. Figure 1 shows a nominated offset of 3 and an illustration of how cell G3 is a summation of cells G2 and F3, a non-absolute rule copied across all cells except for column A, row 1 and cell B2.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
1		1	1	2	3	5	7	11	13	17	19	23	29	31	37	41
2	1	3	4	6	9	14	21	32	45	62	81	104	133	164	201	24
3	1	4	8	14	23	37	=F3+G2	90	135	197	278	382	515	679	880	112
4	2	6	14	28	51	88	146	236	371	568	846	1228	1743	2422	3302	442
5	3	9	23	51	102	190	336	572	943	1511	2357	3585	5328	7750	11052	154
6	5	14	37	88	190	380	716	1288	2231	3742	6099	9684	15012	22762	33814	492

Figure 1 – Pascal’s Triangle mapped to successive primes and given a nominated offset.

In order to check for prime numbers, a separate table on the same spreadsheet was made referring back to the number grid, using the function shown below to populate the cells with a ‘+’ to denote the presence of a prime number in the reference cell, or to fill the cell with a blank space (“ ”) to indicate a non-prime integer in the reference cell. The following function was used to check whether a number was prime:

=IF(A1=2,"+",IF(AND(MOD(A1,ROW(INDIRECT("2:"&ROUNDUP(SQRT(A1),0))))<>0),"+", " ")).

This formula was modified slightly from the formula discussed on www.excelexchange.com/prime_number_test.html.

This source explains that *“this is an array formula (which) relies on Excel’s MOD function to calculate the remainder on every whole number divisor from 2 to the square root of the test number. If there is always a remainder then the number is prime. Excel’s ability to calculate the remainder fails when the test number exceeds 268,435,455.”*

The pattern seen when odd numbers are highlighted (a modulo 2 plot of a binomial triangle) is a fractal known as Sierpiński’s Triangle. (Bannink & Buhrman, 2007). Additional to this second table showing the position of primes in the first table, conditional formatting

using the formula =MOD(A1,2)=1 shows how the position of primes propagated within the triangle move about these set odd number areas (the light green cells) as the offset is manipulated. Graphs were observed for all offsets between -30 and 30.

Figure 2 – showing the position of primes for offset= 3, within the confines of where odd numbers can propagate (shown as light green coloured cells in the rightmost graph, which is also reporting primes in the binomial triangle).

Findings:

It was found that mapping the triangle to primes in the way described above did not affect the odd/even distribution of the numbers propagated, since the binomial triangle does still have symmetry. It was further found that manipulating the offset (cell B2) did not change this odd/even distribution: the conditional formatting highlighting a modulo 2 plotting of the propagated numbers showed the same familiar Sierpiński fractal pattern as the offset was manually altered.

It was found that with an offset of -1 primes populated around the top of the odd/even distribution with a line of primes leading along and down from the input prime 13, as well as primes surrounding the smaller upper even areas.

Figure 3 – showing the position of primes for offset= -1, within the confines of where odd numbers can propagate.

1	1	1	2	3	5	7	11	13						2	3	5	7	11	13
1	-1	0	2	5	10	17	28	41						2	5		17		41
1	0	0	2	7	17	34	62	103						2	7	17			103
2	2	2	4	11	28	62	124	227		2	2	2		11					227
3	5	7	11	22	50	112	236	463		3	5	7	11						463
5	10	17	28	50	100	212	448	911		5		17							911
7	17	34	62	112	212	424	872	1783		7	17								1783
11	28	62	124	236	448	872	1744	3527		11									3527
13	41	103	227	463	911	1783	3527	7054		13	41	103	227	463	911	1783	3527		

Figure 4 – showing rows/columns 1-9 of a prime mapped binomial triangle with a -1 offset, with and then without non-prime integers.

These following graphics show a Sierpiński’s Triangle overlaid onto the number grid (first row/column through to row/column starting 29) resulting from a -1 offset in cell B2. The colour of the areas containing primes have been inverted to show their positioning along the edges of the areas populated by even numbers. For clarity, 2’s have not been highlighted as prime in these graphics, and propagated primes have been shown in green.

Figure 5 – Sierpiński’s Triangle overlaid upon the number grid shown in fig. 3

Figure 6 -Sierpiński’s Triangle overlaid upon the number grid shown in fig. 3. and given a 45° clockwise rotation.

References:

Bannink, T and Buhrman, H (2017) *Quantum Pascal's Triangle and Sierpinski's carpet*. Cornell University / arXiv:1708.07429

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